

A New Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Traces of Benzene Hexachloride (Lindane) in Water

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BENZENEHEXACHLORIDE (BHC) commonly known as γ -BHC, gammexane and lindane, is a potent insecticide by ingestion and by contact¹. The threshold limit of lindane on specified agricultural commodities is 10 ppm by weight for lindane and 5 ppm by weight for BHC². Several instrumental methods including spectrophotometric methods are reported for the determination of BHC³⁻⁷. The present communication reports a new spectrophotometric method for the determination of traces of BHC.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spekol with 1 cm matched silica cells was used for the spectral measurements.

Activated charcoal (freed from impurities⁷), purified ether, a 0.1% aqueous sodium nitrite solution, a 3% aqueous sulphamic acid solution⁸, a 0.2% of 1-naphthol solution in 25% alcohol, 1:5 (v/v) ratio of nitrating mixture⁶ of fuming nitric acid and concentrated sulphuric acid, 0.1 M EDTA and 6 M sodium hydroxide were used.

Procedure :

The method involves four major steps—extraction, dechlorination, reduction, diazotisation and coupling.

Extraction of BHC from water and cereals by activated charcoal : Known amount of BHC was extracted from water (50 ml–2 lit) by means of activated charcoal (~1 g) by shaking. The solution was then filtered and the charcoal with the BHC adsorbed on its surface was placed directly in the reaction flask for further treatment. For cereals, known amount of BHC was added to the crushed samples and extracted with ether, thereafter BHC was adsorbed on charcoal for further treatment.

Dechlorination of BHC and subsequent nitration of benzene to m-dinitrobenzene : Wilson's procedure⁹ as modified by Paul and Gupta¹⁰ was used for the dechlorination of BHC as well as for the nitration of benzene⁸. The sampling train consisted of a dechlorination apparatus (impinger) placed on a water-bath at ~80°. The dechlorination apparatus was now heated gently controlling the heat and gentle stream of air was drawn through it for 45 min at the rate of 0.025–0.1 dm³ min⁻¹ for ~100% adsorption. To the treated dechlorination apparatus, glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added dropwise. The resulting benzene obtained by dechlorination of

BHC was collected in two impingers, each containing 10 ml of nitrating mixture. The nitrated benzene was then reduced, diazotised and coupled by the reported method^{8,11}.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance of red coloured azo dye was measured at 530 nm against distilled water as reference.

1 g of charcoal was required for extraction of BHC from 50 ml–2 lit of water. BHC may be eluted from charcoal by means of glacial acetic acid (recovery ~85%) or alternatively the charcoal with BHC adsorbed on its surface may be directly placed in the reaction flask (recovery ~100%).

1 g of zinc dust and 10 ml of glacial acetic acid were required for dechlorination. 5–10 mg of zinc dust and an acidity range of 0.5–2 M hydrochloric acid were required for reduction. An acidity range of 0.5–5 M hydrochloric acid and 5 min were needed for complete diazotisation. Full colour was developed in 5 min and the dye was stable for more than 30 h.

Beer's law is valid in the range 0.25–2.2 ppm of BHC. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.12 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0026 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.008 and $\pm 1.60\%$ respectively, for a solution containing 32 μg of BHC analysed for a period of 10 days.

The method was found to be free from the interference of other pesticides, inorganic pollutants and benzene free organic pollutants like aldehydes, phenols, ether and alcohols.

Application of method : To a mixture of known amount of BHC free samples of polluted water and the crushed sample of cereals, was added known amount of BHC. It was then shaken with activated charcoal and the amount of BHC was estimated by the proposed method. The recoveries are shown in Table 1. The method was also applied to determine BHC in locally available cereals in which BHC was added for storing purpose, and the results agreed well with the method of Hancock⁷.

TABLE 1—APPLICATION OF THE METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF BHC IN VARIOUS SAMPLES

Sample	Set no	Amount of BHC added	Amount of BHC found*	Percentage recovery
		μg	μg	
Tap water ^a	1	10	9 10	91 0
	2	20	17 91	89 5
	3	40	36 20	90 5
Pond water ^a	1	10	9 12	91 2
	2	20	17 92	89 6
	3	40	36 12	90 3
River water ^a	1	10	9 14	91 4
	2	20	18 34	91 7
	3	40	36 45	91 1

(Table 1 contd.)

Wheat ^b	1	10	9.10	91.0
	2	20	17.93	89.6
	3	40	36.20	90.5
Rice ^b	1	10	8.95	89.5
	2	20	18.32	91.6
	3	40	35.88	89.7
Beans ^b	1	10	8.97	89.7
	2	20	18.12	90.6
	3	40	36.56	91.4

*Mean of three replicate analyses.

^aAmount of sample = 50 ml

^b10 g of each sample was thoroughly washed prior to analysis and then BHC added.

The proposed method is sensitive, selective and superior to the Hancock's method as in the latter the dye formed is stable for only 5 min as compared to 30 h in the present method.

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Ir and Thermal Studies of Absorption Behaviour of Carbon Dioxide, Hydrogen Sulphide and Ammonia on Partially Silver(I)- and Nickel(II)-exchanged 5A Zeolites

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THE present study is devoted to using Ag^I and Ni^{II} ions for cation exchange with synthetic zeolite 5A and the new exchanged forms for interaction with carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and

ammonia, to prepare adsorbed derivatives. These adsorbed derivatives have been investigated by ir spectroscopic and thermal methods. Physical or chemical adsorption of gases is clearly indicated by ir adsorption bands. Discrete steps for the desorption of adsorbed and coordinated species as well as oxidation of reacted molecules have been reported together with weight loss data.

Commercial 5A zeolite, Ca₆Al₁₂Si₁₂O₄₈·30H₂O^I (Union Carbide) in powdered form was repeatedly treated with a saturated aqueous silver(I) nitrate and nickel(II) nitrate (both AnalaR). The resulting partially exchanged Ag^I and Ni^{II}-zeolite were filtered, washed free of excess ions and dried in air. A portion of these samples was interacted with gaseous carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and ammonia in oxygen and moisture free environment. The ir spectra were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out in air at heating rate of 15° min⁻¹ upto 1000° on a Stanton Redcroft STA 780 automatic derivatograph.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of carbon dioxide adsorbed Ag^I-exchanged 5A zeolite reveal only a weak band at about 2 310 cm⁻¹ due to the ν₃ vibration of physically adsorbed carbon dioxide. In the case of hydrogen sulphide adsorbed black derivative of Ag^I-5A zeolite, the bands become more intense especially at 460, 3 410 and 1 640 cm⁻¹ suggesting the formation of silver sulphide and water molecules respectively due to the oxidation of hydrogen sulphide^{2,3}. There is also a broad and weak band at 1 200–955 cm⁻¹ suggesting the inclusion of adsorbed species within the zeolite framework⁴. Ammonia adsorption on Ag^I-exchanged zeolite produces the characteristically strong bands at 1 400 cm⁻¹ (HNH vibration), 3 400 (NH stretch) and 1 635 cm⁻¹ (NH bending) besides ν_{OH} and δ_{OH} vibrations. The ir spectra of carbon dioxide adsorbed Ni^{II}-zeolite exhibit band at 1 410 cm⁻¹ which represents carbonate formation. Adsorption of hydrogen sulphide produces bands around 1 410 (HS) and 450 cm⁻¹ (Ni-S). Adsorption of ammonia increases the intensity of hydroxyl stretching band at around 3 500 cm⁻¹. The band at 1 400 cm⁻¹ (HNH) is quite distinct.

TG analysis (Table 1) of carbon dioxide adsorbed Ag^I-zeolite derivative shows that after dehydration proceeding upto 190°, further weight-loss occurs upto 480° due to desorption of carbon dioxide. Weight-loss after 860° suggests decomposition. The hydrogen sulphide adsorbed Ag^I-zeolite loses weight in three steps. After dehydration and dehydroxylation proceeding upto 340°, there is a sharp weight-loss upto about 780° due to oxidation and decomposition of the adsorbed species. Ammonia adsorbed sample gives weight-loss of about 15%. There are also distinct steps for dehydration, desorption and decomposition of the adsorbed species. TG plot of